

Data Management Plan for Measuring the Open Science Practices in the Digital Humanities

Domain

Version 1

Description

This data management plan (DMP) concerns the data used and produced for a study investigating the current state of openness in DH research practices, with a focus on research data management documentation and peer review processes. In particular, this study addresses two research questions: (1) to what extent DH publications that describe data explicitly reference external documentation detailing data creation and management processes; and (2) how widely open peer review practices are adopted across DH conferences and journals. In this DMP, we detail all the datasets and software related to the study.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for Research and Development in Social Sciences and Humanities (corda____he::101188018)

Researchers

Silvio Peroni (orcid:0000-0003-0530-4305)

Organizations

University of Bologna – Dipartimento di Filologia Classica e
Italianistica

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for Measuring the Open Science Practices in the Digital Humanities Domain](#)

Description:

This data management plan (DMP) concerns the data used and produced for a study investigating the current state of openness in DH research practices, with a focus on research data management documentation and peer review processes. In particular, this study addresses two research questions: (1) to what extent DH publications that describe data explicitly reference external documentation detailing data creation and management processes; and (2) how widely open peer review practices are adopted across DH conferences and journals. In this DMP, we detail all the datasets and software related to the study.

Researchers:

[Silvio Peroni \(orcid:0000-0003-0530-4305\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Bologna – Dipartimento di Filologia Classica e Italianistica](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for Research and Development in Social Sciences and Humanities \(corda_____he::101188018\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Computational Workflows to Measure the Open Science Practices in the Digital Humanities Domain

Open Science has become a central framework for promoting transparency, accessibility, and inclusiveness in scholarly research. While the Digital Humanities (DH) community has long embraced openness in terms of research outputs, less attention seems to have been paid to the openness of the methodological and evaluative processes underlying knowledge production. This software has been developed to gather and analyse the data of an exploratory study that investigates the current state of openness in DH research practices, focusing specifically on research data management documentation and peer review processes. In particular, this study addresses two research questions: (1) to what extent DH publications that describe data explicitly reference external documentation detailing data creation and management processes; and (2) how widely open peer review practices are adopted across DH conferences and journals. The results revealed a limited adoption of open methodological practices. Only a small fraction of the analysed articles provided explicit and reusable documentation of data creation workflows, while no references to data management plans or formal research data management documentation were found. An even more critical picture emerges from the analysis of peer review practices: the vast majority of DH venues continue to rely on traditional single- or double-blind review models, with open peer review practices being adopted only in a few isolated cases.

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

Contact Name	Contact ID	E-mail address	Affiliation
Peroni, Silvio	0000-0003-0530-4305	silvio.peroni@unibo.it	Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

Contributor Name	Contributor ID	E-mail address	Affiliation	Role
Peroni, Silvio	0000-0003-0530-4305	silvio.peroni@unibo.it	Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy	Creator

1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

Some of the project GRAPHIA's (Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for Research and Development in Social Sciences and Humanities, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188018>) funds have covered the costs of the software developer. Instead, Zenodo and Software Heritage are used to archive it at no cost.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.1 Work package and task number

WP	Task
WP3	T3.1

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Software

2 Summary

2.3 Identification of software

2.3.1 Are you re-using already existing software?

No

2.3.3 Creating new software

This software includes two distinct workflows, described in Jupyter Notebooks, that detail the automatic and manual steps required to obtain the data for the analysis and the final graphs that detail specific aspects of the considered DH venues. The Jupyter Notebooks contain appropriate code and natural-language documentation to understand the workflow's rationale and execute it. We did not reuse existing software for this activity due to the specific nature of the analysis to be performed.

2.4 Software characteristics

2.4.1 Software name

Computational Workflows to Measure the Open Science Practices in the Digital Humanities Domain

2.4.2 Type of software

Workflow

2.4.3 Software formats

.ipynb

2.4.4 Size of software

kilobytes (KB)

Comment:

The total storage used by the software is 74 KB, including the two Jupyter Notebooks, the license file, and the readme file.

2.4.5 How is software created/used

The software has been created using common practices in creating Jupyter Notebook documents. In particular, it has been created and used on a MacBook Air (M2 2022) with 24 GB of RAM and macOS Tahoe 26.3.1 installed. The version of Python adopted was Python 3.14.2.

2.4.6 Why is the software created/used

The software was created to gather appropriate information to:

1. check if data papers published in Journal of Open Humanities Data (JOHD) include references or mentions to external material appropriately dedicated to either describing the management of the data a paper describes, such as a Data Management Plan (DMP), or detailing precisely the workflow used to produce these data, e.g. published as a particular workflow document or as a computational notebook;

2. identify the practice of reviewing processes established in some DH venues, including conferences and journals, tracking how many venues adopt open peer review processes instead of the classic ones that prescribe either the sole anonymity of reviewers (single-blind from now on) or the anonymity of both authors and reviewers (double-blind from now on).

2.4.7 Software description

This software enables to gather and analyse data to answer two specific research questions:

1. How many publications which describe some data contain an explicit reference to external documentation detailing the process used to create and maintain such data, such as a DMP and/or a detailed workflow depicting the process of data creation?
2. How many DH venues adopt open peer reviewing practices?

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

The software should be preserved to guarantee the reproducibility of the experiment described in the article "Are Digital Humanities really committed to open? An exploratory study on the availability of methodological workflows and open peer review practices", accepted at the AIUCD Conference 2026.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19758644	Yes	Yes	Generalist
Software Heritage	https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:5f57b4c5f27b2e8710e5b702e33a38c254a2487e;origin=https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19758643;visit=swh:1:snp:5d8cdba62da00feca458c8443e28ead5186c1c96;anchor=s	No	Yes	Discipline specific

	wh:1:rel:7bf386e589101f3e3f45960968618727d903ac3b;path=essepuntato-dh-open-b492c8b			
GitHub	https://github.com/essepuntato/dh-open/tree/v1.0.0	No	No	Discipline specific

4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

We decided to add the software in three different repositories to guarantee a better long-term preservation and, thus, to enable the reproducibility of the experiment where the software has been used.

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
doi	10.5281/zenodo.19758644
swhid	swh:1:dir:a790e56868864e6f28b35901eb80c808dc55edc5;origin=https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19758643;visit=swh:1:snp:5d8cdba62da00feca458c8443e28ead5186c1c96;anchor=swh:1:rel:7bf386e589101f3e3f45960968618727d903ac3b;path=/essepuntato-dh-open-b492c8b/

4.2.2 Metadata

DataCite Metadata Schema for Zenodo, and Software Heritage Metadata Schema for Software Heritage.

4.2.3 Keywords

Digital Humanities, Open Science Practices, Open Peer Review, Research Data Management

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

The software is accessible in all three repositories mentioned (Zenodo, Software Heritage, GitHub).

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

No particular software development methodology has been strictly followed in creating the two Jupyter Notebook documents that define the software. They have been developed using a system, i.e. Jupyter Notebook, that runs on different operating systems, including Linux, Mac and Windows.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

No particular vocabulary has been used. The primary programming language for implementing the computational part of the workflows is Python.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

other

Comment:

The license used is ISC - <https://opensource.org/license/isc>. This license provides permission to use, copy, modify, and/or distribute this software for any purpose with or without fee, provided that the above copyright notice and this permission notice appear in all copies.

4.5.2 Documentation

Both workflows are largely documented in natural language, explaining precisely what each piece of code does. The natural-language documentation is encapsulated within the Jupyter Notebook documents that implement the workflows.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

Before releasing it, the workflows' execution has been tested several times to ensure that both workflows work as expected. In particular, the outcomes of their execution have been checked by hand on a random subset.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

During development, the software was stored on a local hard drive and in a cloud solution (Dropbox) to avoid losing it due to an unpredictable issue with the local PC.

5.2.2 Backup

The Dropbox cloud service adopted has a backup facility that enable to track back the history of the files it preserves.

5.2.3 Additional security

There was no need to implement additional security measures.

Full-text data papers from JOHD and call for papers from DH venues

This dataset contains the data used in the paper entitled "Are Digital Humanities really committed to open? An exploratory study on the availability of methodological workflows and open peer review practices", accepted at the [AIUCD Conference 2026](#). The aim of this work is to answer to two specific research questions (RQ1 and RQ2), i.e.:

1. How many publications which describe some data contain an explicit reference to external documentation detailing the process used to create and maintain such data, such as a DMP and/or a detailed workflow depicting the process of data creation?
2. How many DH venues adopt open peer reviewing practices?

We have run an exploratory study considering specific research venues. In particular:

- To address RQ1, we check if data papers published in [Journal of Open Humanities Data \(JOHD\)](#) include references or mentions to external material appropriately dedicated to either describing the management of the data a paper describes, such as a Data Management Plan (DMP), or detailing precisely the workflow used to produce these data, e.g. published as a particular workflow document or as a computational notebook;
- To address RQ2, we identify the practice of reviewing processes established in some DH venues, including conferences and journals, tracking how many venues adopt open peer review processes instead of the classic ones that prescribe either the sole anonymity of reviewers (single-blind from now on) or the anonymity of both authors and reviewers (double-blind from now on).

The dataset contains two folders containing the data to address the aforementioned RQs. In particular:

- the folder data/ includes the sources of the data papers (in PDF and XML formats) published in JOHD in 2025, all published in open access using appropriate Creative Commons licenses (i.e. CC BY) - the correct license attribution can be retrieved from the journal website;
- the folder cfp/ includes all the call for papers (in HTML, PDF and TXT formats) of the following venues:

the past five years (2022-2026) of the annual conference organised by the [Associazione per l'Informatica Umanistica e la Cultura Digitale \(AIUCD\)](#);

the past five years (2022-2026) of the annual conference organised by the [Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations \(ADHO\)](#);

the DH journals in the list available at <https://dhjournals.github.io/list/>, in particular those that are (a) completely devoted to publishing DH articles, (b) still active, (c) have a URL associated, and (d) specify a standard article submission procedure.

In addition, both folders also contain the data (in JSON and CSV formats, released using the CC0 waiver to maximise their reuse) resulting from the analysis conducted by executing two distinct workflows devised for addressing the aforementioned research questions. Both workflows have been defined using Jupyter Notebook and are available in the following document:

Peroni, S. (2026). Computational Workflows to Measure the Open Science Practices in the Digital Humanities Domain (Version v1.0.0) [Computer software]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19758644>

Template: [Data Management Plan Template - University of Bologna](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Your research output

1.1 Contact details and responsibilities

1.1.1 Contact person(s)

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1.1.3 Research output creator(s) and contributor(s)

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1.1.4 Institution(s) involved

University of Bologna

1.2 Resources for data management

1.2.1 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR?

Some of the project GRAPHIA's (Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for Research and Development in Social Sciences and Humanities, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188018>) funds have covered

the costs of the software developer. Instead, Zenodo and Software Heritage are used to archive it at no cost.

1.3 Identifying the research output

1.3.1 Work package and task number

WP	Task
WP3	T3.1

1.3.2 Which type of research output are you describing?

Dataset

2 Summary

2.1 Identification of the dataset

2.1.1 Are you re-using an already existing dataset?

No

2.1.3 Creating a new dataset

No dataset containing the needed data for the intended analysis to perform were available.

2.2 Dataset characteristics

2.2.1 Dataset name

Full-text data papers from JOHD and call for papers from DH venues

2.2.2 Data types

- a. numerical
- b. quantitative
- c. qualitative
- d. textual

e. tabular

2.2.3 Data formats

a. .csv

b. .json

c. .pdf

d. .html

e. .txt

2.2.4 Size of data

megabytes (MB)

Comment:

The total amount of data storage is 71.6 MB.

2.2.5 How is the data generated/collected

The data have been produced by executing the workflows in the following document:

Peroni, S. (2026). Computational Workflows to Measure the Open Science Practices in the Digital Humanities Domain (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19758644>

2.2.6 Why is the data generated/collected

The data were generated to answer two specific research questions:

1. How many publications which describe some data contain an explicit reference to external documentation detailing the process used to create and

maintain such data, such as a DMP and/or a detailed workflow depicting the process of data creation?

2. How many DH venues adopt open peer reviewing practices?

2.2.7 Dataset description

The dataset comprises two folders of data to address the aforementioned RQs. In particular:

- the folder data/ includes the sources of the data papers (in PDF and XML formats) published in JOHD in 2025, all published in open access using appropriate Creative Commons licenses (i.e. CC BY) - the correct license attribution can be retrieved from the journal website;
- the folder cfp/ includes all the call for papers (in HTML, PDF and TXT formats) of the following venues: (a) the past five years (2022-2026) of the annual conference organised by the Associazione per l'Informatica Umanistica e la Cultura Digitale (AIUCD); (b) the past five years (2022-2026) of the annual conference organised by the Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (ADHO); (c) the DH journals in the list available at <https://dhjournals.github.io/list/>, in particular those that are (a) completely devoted to publishing DH articles, (b) still active, (c) have a URL associated, and (d) specify a standard article submission procedure.

In addition, both folders also contain the data (in JSON and CSV formats, released using the CC0 waiver to maximise their reuse) resulting from the analysis conducted by executing two distinct workflows devised for addressing the aforementioned research questions.

3 Ethics and legal aspects

3.1 Personal data

3.1.1 Are you handling personal data?

No

3.2 Legal aspects

3.2.1 Are there any legal issues associated to your output? (e.g. IPR or valorization)

No

3.3 Other ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there other ethical issues associated to your output?

No

4 Making research FAIR

4.1 Long-term preservation

4.1.1 Selecting what to preserve

All the data should be preserved since they enable us to scrutinise and reproduce the content of an academic paper - i.e. "Are Digital Humanities really committed to open? An exploratory study on the availability of methodological workflows and open peer review practices", accepted at the AIUCD Conference 2026.

4.1.2 Chosen repository/ies

Name	Link	Is your repository OpenAIRE compliant?	Is your repository catalogued in re3data?	What type of repository is it?
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/records/19758167	Yes	Yes	Generalist

4.1.3 Further information on long-term preservation strategy

The long-term preservation of the data should be guaranteed by Zenodo, one of the primary repositories worldwide operated by CERN.

4.2 Findability

4.2.1 Persistent identifier(s)

Type of PID (e.g., DOI, Handle)	PID (e.g., doi.org/10...)
doi	10.5281/zenodo.19758167

4.2.2 Metadata

DataCite Metadata Schema (as provided by Zenodo).

4.2.3 Keywords

Digital Humanities, Open Science Practices, Open Peer Review, Research Data Management

4.3 Accessibility

4.3.1 Is the research output openly accessible?

Yes

4.3.3 Accessing the research output

All the data can be downloaded freely via Zenodo, following the persistent identifier (DOI) listed above.

4.3.4 Is metadata openly accessible?

Yes

4.4 Interoperability

4.4.1 Methodologies

All data have been produced using standard formats (CSV, JSON, TXT, XML, PDF) to enable and maximise their interoperability across different studies and software.

4.4.2 Vocabularies, taxonomies and other standards

No particular vocabulary - or other semantic artefacts - has been used to model the data exposed in this dataset.

4.5 Reusability

4.5.1 Licensing

other

Comment:

All data (PDF, XML, TXT) gathered from existing sources (e.g. the data paper full-texts and the call for papers from the related venues' websites) are released using the licenses originally specified by the providers - primarily CC BY. Instead, all the data produced (CSV, JSON) by elaborating such source data are available under CC0 to maximise their reuse.

4.5.2 Documentation

The dataset documentation has been added to the metadata of the record uploaded to Zenodo.

5 Quality and security

5.1 Quality of the research output

5.1.1 Measures implemented to ensure quality

A portion of the data used and produced has been checked by hand. In particular, we selected a random sample of data papers and call-for-papers to verify that each document and its related elaborated outputs were aligned with the expected information to be extracted, since part of the data has been gathered and processed automatically.

5.2 Security measures

5.2.1 Storage

Cloud Storage Services

Comment:

We have used Dropbox as a complementary cloud service to store the data we generated during development, in addition to keeping it available on a local machine.

5.2.2 Backup

Dropbox provides a backup of the data so that previous versions can be retrieved in case an issue arises on the local machine where the data was generated.

5.2.3 Additional security

No additional protection is needed, considering the nature of the data.

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